

INTERACTIVE METHODS OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

Sharipova Nilufar Mavlonovna

Teacher at Gulistan State University

nilufarsharipovamavlonovna@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16736248>

Abstract: This article highlights the content of modern pedagogical technologies, their role and importance in the educational process, and the impact of interactive methods on teaching effectiveness. The article analyzes innovative approaches, the modernization of the educational process, and the role of interactive methods in developing independent thinking skills in students.

Keywords: modern pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, innovation, educational effectiveness, independent thinking, brainstorming, case study, blitz, teaching, teaching techniques, lecture, storytelling.

Introduction

One of the main tasks facing the education system in today's globalization process is the formation of a competitive, creative-thinking individual with practical knowledge and skills. This requires an innovative approach from teachers, a deep mastery of modern pedagogical technologies, and the application of interactive methods in the teaching process.

Consistent work is being carried out to reform the education system in the country through the implementation of tasks defined in the Action Strategy on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, training highly qualified personnel in accordance with labor market requirements, introducing international standards for assessing education quality, and creating effective mechanisms for implementing innovative scientific achievements in practice. There is a growing demand for the effective organization of activities of teachers who take an innovative approach to training competitive and internationally recognized skilled workers and specialists meeting employer requirements, as well as instructors of vocational training courses for the unemployed population and masters of industrial training.

In accordance with the tasks set for the professional education system, it is necessary to implement objectives such as increasing the effectiveness of the educational process in educational institutions, introducing the latest scientific achievements into practice, and nurturing a creative, socially active, spiritually rich, professionally skilled, and harmoniously developed individual, raised in the spirit of national and universal values. To accomplish these tasks, it is essential for the pedagogical teams of educational institutions to make a fundamental shift in their pedagogical approach.

Main part

The essence of modern pedagogical technologies

Modern pedagogical technologies are a set of methods aimed at the scientifically based, systematic, and effective organization of the educational process. These include: modular learning, problem-based learning, the use of information and communication technologies (ICT), e-learning, collaborative learning, and others. The active work of modern educators in

these processes, along with a number of professional qualities, requires a level of readiness for innovative activity. The level of aptitude for such activity is clearly manifested in the project of educational technology and the pedagogical idea at its center. If the creator of educational technology - the teacher - possesses theoretical knowledge, practical experience, and the skill of applying advanced teaching methods and techniques, the quality and effectiveness of education are guaranteed.

Since any teaching technology is directed towards a specific didactic goal, it is based on a specific pedagogical idea. Since the essence of pedagogical technologies consists of the idea of developing the learner's personality in various aspects, the same idea operates on the basis of educational technologies on various topics. However, each time an attempt is made to find a new, original answer to the question: in what form, by what methods, and how should this idea be implemented? From this "response," the essence of the pedagogical idea that drives the technology is understood.

At the stages of continuous education, interactive methods that serve to ensure the effectiveness of educational technologies are widely used. The names of dozens of methods, such as "6x6x6," "brainstorming," "pinboarding," "coaching," "case study," "project training," are understandable and familiar to everyone. When planning their use in educational practice, the teacher takes the didactic goal as a basis. At this moment, he ponders how to achieve this goal. To solve the problem, it is necessary to create a specific idea. So, the didactic goal is clear, the stages of its implementation and teaching methods are defined, but what is the basis of educational technology?

In the "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan," "An idea is a thought that arises in human thought and leads society and people to a goal. It embodies the goals of knowing and changing the world, the ways and means of achieving them." If we apply this definition to pedagogical technologies, then the definition arises as "the study of optimal options for the creation, application, and unification of teaching and learning methods." Variants of pedagogical technologies aimed at developing students' speech are the result of the creative activity of the teacher-pedagogues who developed them. At the heart of this activity lies a certain view, the idea of ensuring the effectiveness of education.

Interactive methods: concepts and types

Interactive methods are forms of teaching based on active communication between the student and the teacher, which increase students' activity in learning during the lesson, form independent thinking and problem-solving skills. Popular interactive methods:

- "Brainstorming"
- "Cluster" method
- "Blitz-survey"
- "Debate" and "Discussion"
- "Role Playing" and "Situational Exercises"
- "Fishbone," "INSERT," "Syncwine" and other graphic methods.

Pedagogical technologies ensure the implementation of the main directions of pedagogical strategy, the humanization of education and a systematic approach focused on the individual, that is, the mental development of the student, their independence, and kindness to the teacher and to each other. The peculiarity of innovative pedagogical technologies requires special attention to the individuality of a person, the development of

their creative activity, and their personality. In scientific and pedagogical literature, there are various definitions of the concept of "pedagogical (educational) technology."

Advantages of interactive methods

- Develops students' thinking and creative potential.
- Increases activity in lessons, reduces passivity.
- Creates an atmosphere of cooperation between strong and weak students.
- Develops the ability to quickly find solutions in problem situations.
- Prepares for discussions, debates, and teamwork.

Pedagogical conditions for the application of interactive methods

For interactive methods to yield effective results in the educational process, the following pedagogical conditions must be considered:

- Formation of students' confidence in free thinking
- Creating a positive psychological environment
- Selection of methods corresponding to the lesson topic
- Ensuring the active participation of each participant
- Encouraging analytical thinking and generalization activities.

The authors of the idea of the problem-based learning technology are T.V. Kudryavtsev, M. Matyushkin, V. Okon, and M.I. Makhmutov. The purpose of pedagogical technology is aimed at the formation of independent creative research abilities of the student, aimed at solving educational problems under the guidance of a teacher. The application of pedagogical technology leads to the formation in the student of new knowledge, skills and abilities, developing cognitive abilities, erudition (knowledge, intelligence), love of knowledge, creative thinking, and other important personal qualities and abilities.

In this technology, the teacher does not convey knowledge in a ready-made form, but creates a problem situation for the student on the topic and creates conditions for the awakening of thoughts and ideas about solving the problem.

Interactive learning technology has a number of methods used in conducting classes, which allow the development of critical thinking of students in the group, as well as the following:

activation of students' cognitive processes, development of communication skills, teamwork skills necessary in the process of communication with teachers and interaction, ensuring the activity-based nature of training;

contributing to the development of such professional qualities as analysis, predicting the development of the situation, forming and expressing one's position, adequate perception and assessment of information;

contributes to the realization of the possibility of creative search for ways to solve problems and has a significant emotional impact due to the exciting, competitive, and creative nature of the activity.

Methods used in vocational education are classified into two types: active and interactive methods.

Active methods provide for the student's position towards the teacher. During the lesson, students use individual textbooks, notebooks, and computers. Active methods are aimed at revealing the creative potential of the student and their communication skills, forming their own opinion and the ability to justify it. Interacting with the external objective

world, the individual acquires practical experience of perception and finds ways to influence it.

As for interactive methods, thanks to them, the knowledge acquired by students through their interaction with each other is mastered. Methods are aimed at the joint work of students in small groups and the performance of individual tasks through the form of joint work of students. Interactive methods are used in small groups, excursions, business games, creative tasks and exercises, etc.

The teacher's role in interactive teaching methodology changes significantly. Now he acts not as a manager, but as a coordinator of the process. Its task is to prepare interactive tasks and topics for discussion, to advise and monitor the implementation of the curriculum. During the process, the teacher and students communicate with each other, discuss issues, defend their personal points of view, and reach a compromise.

In the process of teaching, along with the application of methods, teaching techniques can also be used.

Teaching technique is a generalized set of pedagogical methods and teaching aids that optimizes the learning process without exceeding the limits of the applied method. Teaching techniques include INSERT, pinboards, expert surveys, and others.

Teaching methods, which determine the style of joint activity of the teacher (teaching) and the student (acquisition of knowledge) in achieving the educational goal, can be divided into 4 groups according to their nature and the result of the educational process.

Lecture - a monologic presentation by a teacher of a large volume of educational material over a long period of time. An informative lecture is a brief (10-15 minutes) presentation of the main content of a topic in the form of information.

A story is an emotional message from the teacher about an event, phenomenon, or truth, usually used to clarify theoretical situations and generate interest in the material being studied. The content of the material in the story consists of an artistic, expressive, and emotional presentation in simple language through examples.

Explanation is a method of verbal expression, which consists of expressing, analyzing, and interpreting educational material through various arguments.

Instruction is a teaching method that helps to complete a learning task through additional explanation.

Through demonstration, commentary, and explanation, the teacher teaches students a specific sequence of actions for completing the task, ways to implement it, a description of certain situations, and ways to apply them in practice. Instruction is carried out through instruction.

Demonstration is the visual-emotional familiarization of learners with objects, phenomena, and processes in their natural form.

Demonstration involves the visual representation and perception of objects, processes, and phenomena.

Video method - a method based on visual assimilation of information, carried out using computers that display educational material or information on an electronic board, projector, television, educational television programs, as well as on a display.

Methods belonging to the 2nd group of teaching methods mainly ensure the conscious assimilation and consolidation of knowledge in the activities of students through the teacher's explanation and demonstration of actions.

The portfolio serves to provide an opportunity to indirectly assess the activities of the teacher and the student, to analyze their quality and effectiveness. Moreover, portfolios provide teachers and students with the opportunity to indirectly familiarize commission members with their personality and activities during various expert examinations.

In recent years, in modern education, there has been a growing need to improve the content of the teacher's professional activity and the student's educational activity, as well as to adequately and objectively assess the quality of both types of activity based on certain indicators.

In general, the portfolio highlights the maximum achievements of each teacher or student, their creative potential, interests, and abilities. Portfolio is a kind of advertisement for a teacher or student.

Conclusion

Modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods have become an integral part of today's education. They not only involve students in active participation, but also form their skills of independent thinking, analysis of problem situations, and finding solutions. If every teacher enriches their lessons with methods based on modern technologies, this will undoubtedly improve the quality of education.

References:

1. Tokhtasinov B. "Pedagogical Technologies and Interactive Methods," Tashkent, 2020.
2. Hasanboeva M.Q. "Modern Lesson and Interactive Methods," Samarkand, 2021.
- UNESCO. Interactive Pedagogy for 21st Century Learners, Paris, 2019.
4. Marzano R. "Effective Teaching Strategies," USA, 2017.
5. Azizxo'jaeva N.N. "Fundamentals of Pedagogical Technologies," Tashkent, 2018.
6. Avliyoqulov N.X. "Modern Educational Technologies." Tashkent; 2001. - 69 p.
7. Azizxodjayeva N.N. Pedagogical Technologies and Pedagogical Mastery. - T.: Finance, 2003. - 192 p.
8. Seminar-training materials on the topic "Ways to Increase the Effectiveness of Education." Instructions for trainers. / compiling authors A.Nishonov, Haydarov, B.Nuridinov, D.Razzoqov and others. -T.: O'MKHTRI, ADB O'ZB-1737 project, 2002.-112 p.
9. Ishmukhamedov R., Abdukodirov A., Pardayev A. Innovative technologies in education (practical recommendations for teachers of educational institutions). - T.: "Talent" Foundation, 2008. - 180 p.
10. Ishmuhamedov R., Abduqodirov A., Pardayev A. Innovative Technologies in Education (Practical Recommendations for Educational Institution Teachers). - T.; "Iste'dod" Foundation, 2010. -142 p.
11. Yo'ldoshev J.G'.f Usmonov S.A. Fundamentals of Pedagogical Technology. - T.: RTM, 2004. - 104 p.
12. Golish L.V. "Active Teaching Methods: Content, Selection, Implementation." - T.: Tashkent, 2001. - 69 p.
13. Golish L.V. "Modern Educational Technologies: Content, Design, and Implementation" Tashkent: Tasis, 2001. -59 p.